

ACTUAL METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, there is a need to fit into a world increasingly globalized, in which communication and foreign languages have more importance than some years ago. The English language is the language of international communication. Present day English is the simplest adaptation of a very old language and yet it is still difficult to teach this language effectively, especially to those who speak English as a second or even third language. Teaching only the rules is found to be boring by most students and it is because of this that they lose interest in learning the language. Although there is no way other than the traditional one to teach the basics of the language these approaches must be tweaked a bit so as to appeal to the students. When it comes to teaching English to students of higher classes who already know the basics the traditional methods generally tend to yield poorer results than modern and innovative methods. These methods help the students learn the language better without them actually realizing and also it keeps their interest. This paper will provide useful approaches and methods to teach English Language.

The traditional «chalk and talk» method of teaching that's persisted for hundreds of years is now acquiring inferior results when compared with the more modern and revolutionary teaching methods that are available for use in schools today. Greater student interaction is encouraged, the boundaries of authority are being broken down, and a focus on enjoyment over grades is emphasized. Sometimes using same styles in teaching

language may let go down interests of student to language. Some types of teaching in use, not to go down interest to foreign language.

1. Dialogical speech – in this way students have a talk each other by creative approach. «Modern Methodology of Teaching English puts Speaking in Dialogues in the first place for developing speaking skills. These skills can be trained with various teaching aids, including texts of fiction. Such dialogues give an

opportunity to avoid traditional rendering of the texts and turn them into living English speech». More than that, all the vocabulary is remembered much better. In dialogues, students train in fluency, quick reaction, acting skills and, of course, grammatical correctness.

2. Student reads the text himself and tells the meaning. Reading is interactive. Reading short stories, novels and other literary works written by famous Uzbek, English and American writers is very important in language learning. As a teacher of English you may apply a variety of reading strategies, analyze literary elements use a variety of strategies to read unfamiliar words and build vocabulary, prepare, organize, and present literary interpretations.

3. Understanding by listening– by these way students can improve speech skills. Listening is a receptive form of speech activity. Comprehension of speech while listening mainly based on auditory feelings. By perceiving, reproduce what we hear, in the form of inwardly speech. Listening comprehension is impossible without working of speech motor analyzer. Of course internal speaking requires ability to speak in this language. Understanding of sounding speech, in the moment of comprehension, is accompanied by intellectual activity, which includes recognizing of speech means and interpretation of the content.

4. Learning English through the watching movies. Nowadays, teachers take into consideration students' demands for watching real movie stories together with reading books, magazines and newspapers. Because, as it is known not only printed materials can serve as a great source of

teaching but also songs and movies play a key role in learning foreign languages.

5. The importance of teaching Vocabulary. Vocabulary is one of the aspects of the language to be taught in the institutes. In addition to learn new vocabulary, learner need to able to use strategies to cope with unknown vocabulary met in listening or reading text, to make up for gaps in productive vocabulary in speaking and writing to gain fluency in using known vocabulary and to learn new words in isolation. Vocabulary learning is not on end in itself. A rich vocabulary makes to perform the skills of listening, speaking, reading and writing easier [1, p. 116]. By the type of teaching in traditional style is divided into several aspects such as speaking, analytic reading, reading at home, practice grammar, practical phonetics. As a result 3-4 teachers teach students in variety styles and as a result the connection of aspects is not provided.

Some students learn grammar well, but in speech they meet difficulties to pronounce words. On this way we meet some questions. May be it is right, but in the course all aspects of teaching by new style are carrying out parallel. The theory is given, strengthens with different exercises, games, discussions in one class. We've spoken about groups which are got good results in following methods:

- the level of knowledge of students and assimilating possibilities are learned and then tasks are given by this way;
- attracting students' attentions is put into practice fully and none student is never stayed out of attention;
- students speak mainly in foreign language during the lesson, translation of

unclear words aren't told instantly, but they try to realize them with mimics;

- students are divided into small groups and they use these methods: «work out discussions», «speak own opinion», «realize together»;

- make opportunities to students to think and speak minds freely, and their mistakes aren't corrected instantly, but after student speaking they are discussed together;

- different grammar, phonetic and other types of games are organized. In this way roles are shared with students due to their knowledge;

- retell the text, variety pictures and watching short films and discussing them together, listening to news about theme and trying to realize them.

Moreover there are some methods to improve learning foreign language. Lessons are fully taught in English language based on all experiences, which are needed for lessons. That is to say students begin to understand by reading, by listening, practice of writing, improve speech and others. Students are become focal point of lessons, not teachers. The teacher only helps student to get knowledge. In this way the possibility of self-studying is got well [2, p. 156].

When lessons aren't traditional, tasks are divided into couple or small group of students due to the type of it, students work in groups or individually. For instance, at the beginning of lesson teacher makes plan and shares news with students. Each student participates in this plan and shares news with each other's. As a result mutual exchanging of knowledge is appeared and all students get to know the theme. Some exercises are done by couple or group of students. For working in the group students are given such tasks:

organize debates, debate the theme with playing roles and work with high techs. To work in couple they are given dialogues, grammar materials, and also reading. By these methods we can make all students to participate in lesson and teacher can help every student due to his or her demands [2, p. 83].

We wanted to speak that the main thing in learning language is attracting students, that is to say they need motivation. It is necessary to keep activeness of student during and after lessons. The teachers around the world are always in searching about how to teach foreign languages successfully to students.

There are a lot of effective methods of teaching. Among the major differences between the traditional methods and the modern one's is that the modern teaching refers to «Students Centered is teaching», raising the process of teaching on such a scale that it would be not only beneficial but also interesting for learners. Good doses of such activities as Project Work, Development of Dialogues, Speech skills, Group / Pair work, Whole - Class Activities, Motivating Learners, Different Games, Role-play and Physical Activities become essential in Modern Teaching. Today teachers are facing to the following fact: The language teachers need both models and tools. In addition to the essential theory, aims and goals - the vision or pattern of what is to be created - they must gain through study, reflection, trial and error, and experience, the necessary expertise in using the tools essential to success in their craft. They must give serious thought to how they may lift their work to higher levels of usefulness and joy. Teachers who study and use Modern Methods of Teaching English are those who

care about their own value – to self, to family, to society, to a larger community of the world. Finally, these individuals are doers – practical achievers in their chosen profession. That's why we are sure that our work will be of a great value and help the teachers who want to become modern and up – to date professionals [3, p. 146].

Modern Methods of Teaching English can be both challenging and demanding for teachers and students; they can also be very stimulating and rewarding. The degree to which we can adopt these approaches in our institute may well depend on willingness of our students, the proficiency of our teachers and their willingness to accept these Modern Methods, and the availability of resources within our environment.

Moreover, the necessity to improve the level of education at high institutional

levels is obvious nowadays. We are deeply convinced that creating collaborative atmosphere in the classroom, intellectual and informational approaches in teaching, teaching students to derive generalizations, deductive conclusion as well as developing debating abilities and individual study [4, p. 184].

In all of these approaches, the most powerful thing to recognize is that they focus explicitly on engaging both the student and the teacher. When teachers are treated like the intelligent professionals that they are, and given the flexibility to engage in approaches to teaching and learning that go beyond archaic models that they are often bound to, students respond differently, and education is improved.

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